

MAKING HIV PREVENTION WORK:

Supporting Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) Use & Adherence in sub-Saharan Africa

Overview Brief

Why this matters:

Despite multiple proven PrEP options (oral pills, vaginal ring, long-acting injectables), uptake is still far below the UNAIDS 2025 goal of 10 million users. While access has expanded, discontinuation and use outside periods of risk limit the overall impact.

Where we are:

By 2023, more than 3.5 million people had used PrEP globally, nearly 75% in Africa, signalling growing access but persistent gaps in reaching targets.

What's new/coming:

A diversified menu now includes daily oral, event-driven dosing for men who have sex with men (MSM), the monthly dapivirine ring, and long-acting injectables (Cabotegravir every 2 months; Lenacapavir every 6 months) - expanding alignment to user preferences and life contexts.

These trends raise critical questions about which strategies have successfully supported effective PrEP use and what lessons can guide future implementation efforts as additional PrEP options become available.

We conducted a rapid review of evidence in response to direct requests from countries in the [South to South Learning Network \(SSLN\)](#) to better understand:

Which interventions are most effective in improving PrEP adherence?

How are these interventions implemented to overcome barriers?

How does context influence the effectiveness of adherence interventions?

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The framework: *Two dimensions of PrEP effectiveness*

Our review confirmed that effective PrEP implementation depends on progress across two interconnected dimensions:

1. Individual and community readiness:

Personal risk perception, partner and household dynamics, peer norms, stigma, and broader community awareness of PrEP options.

2. Service delivery and system readiness:

Provider training and attitudes, differentiated service delivery, data systems, reliable supply chains, and supportive policy environments.

Source: Mathur S, Pilgrim N, Pulerwitz J. PrEP introduction for adolescent girls and young women. *Lancet HIV* 2016; 3:e406–e408.

Both dimensions must be addressed in tandem: individual motivation without system support leads to frustration and discontinuation; strong systems without community demand lead to under utilisation.

Supporting adherence across PrEP options

Different PrEP modalities require different kinds of adherence support to maximise effectiveness.

Product	Dosing / Frequency	Eligible populations	Successful adherence support
Oral PrEP tenofovir disoproxil and emtricitabine (TDF/FTC)	1 pill daily	All populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reminder systems and multi-month dispensing. • Individual supportive adherence counselling to overcome personal barriers. PrEP education and awareness. • Peer support or mentor programmes. • Inclusion of non-traditional healthcare providers (e.g., pharmacists, Community Health Workers (CHWs)) in PrEP delivery.
Oral PrEP Emtricitabine plus tenofovir alafenamide (FTC/TAF)	1 pill daily	Cisgender men; not recommended for receptive vaginal sex	
Oral PrEP (TDF/XTC)	Event-driven "2-1-1" dosing	Cisgender men (MSM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailored counselling so clients clearly understand the "2-1-1" dosing schedule and when it is appropriate. • PrEP education and awareness. • Peer support or mentor programmes.
Dapivirine vaginal ring (DVR)	1 ring monthly	Cisgender women	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provider and user education on correct insertion/removal and addressing vaginal health concerns. • Individual supportive adherence counselling to overcome personal barriers. • Integration of DVR into existing services (e.g., family planning, STI, gender-based violence).
Injectable Cabotegravir	Day 1 (1st injection); 1 month (2nd); then every 2 months	All populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliable appointment systems, tracking for missed doses, and client reminders. • Individual supportive adherence counselling to overcome personal barriers. • Integration of PrEP into existing services (e.g., family planning, STI clinics).
	Day 1 (injection + oral lead-in); Day 2 (oral); then every 6 months	All populations	
Injectable Lenacapavir	Day 1 (injection + oral lead-in); Day 2 (oral); then every 6 months	All populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong systems to trace clients across longer intervals and flexibility to accommodate mobility and life changes. • Individual supportive adherence counselling to overcome personal barriers. • Integration of PrEP into existing services (e.g., family planning, STI clinics).

Supporting adherence across PrEP options

Tailoring adherence support for each product is essential: clients need the right information, reminders, and provider follow-up to sustain effective prevention throughout periods of risk/vulnerability.

Practical implications for effective PrEP implementation

Choice + Continuity:

Offer modalities side-by-side, enable switching across oral/ring/injectables without penalty, normalise start/rapid re-start of PrEP during periods of vulnerability, and align follow-up to each product's cadence to reduce drop-off.

Provider and Health Systems Enhancement:

Invest in routine, modality-specific competency (e.g., event-driven counselling, injection scheduling & tracing, ring fitting) and bias/stigma reduction, since providers act as frontline gatekeepers.

Community Engagement:

Pair clinic readiness with community awareness and partner engagement to shift norms and increase accurate risk perception. As new PrEP options become available, aligning *user choice* with *system readiness* will be critical to achieve impact at scale.

Additional Resources

To find out more information on how this can be done, please refer to:

- [Learning Brief for Ministry of Health and National Aids Commission Officials](#)
- [Learning Brief for Programme Implementers](#)

To find out more about our review methodology and remaining gaps in knowledge related to PrEP adherence, please refer to:

- [Methodology Brief](#)

The full rapid review slide deck can be accessed [here](#)

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